

Flavonoid Glycosides of *Christella parasitica* (L.) H. Lev. of the Western Ghats of South India

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Christella parasitica (L.) H Lev, a pteridophyte is the largest species complex in South India growing in partially or fully shaded evergreen forests from 800–1200 m¹ Matured aerial part of *C parasitica* (Xavier's College Herbarium, Voucher No 35191) were collected from Tirunelveli hills of the Western Ghats of South India Kaempferol-3-*O*- β -D-glucoside (astragalin) and kaempferol-3-*O*-rutinoside have been isolated and characterised

Air-dried fronds (460 g) of *C parasitica* was extracted with MeOH (3 $\times$ 3 dm³) under reflux for 6 h The extracts and then MeOH (8 dm³) were passed over a column of activated charcoal (50 g) The resulting solution was chromatographed over silica gel (CHCl₃-MeOH) and Sephadex LH-20 (MeOH) to yield compounds **1** (760 mg) and **2** (71 mg)

Mps were determined with a Yanagimoto apparatus and are uncorrected Optical rotations were taken with a JASCO DIP-360 polarimeter Glc was run on a Shimadzu GC-4BM-PF instrument with a flame ionisation detector using a capillary column (30 m $\times$ 0.25 mm id, WCOT SE-30, Wako Pure Chemicals) The ¹H nmr and ¹³C nmr spectra were measured on a Jeol FX-100 spectrometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-2200 spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Shimadzu IR-460 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Hitachi M-80 spectrometer

Compound **1** was obtained as yellow needles m p 184–86^o (MeOH), [α]_D-55^o (c 1.0 pyridine), $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 300, 1 656, 1 600, 1 500, 1 450,

1 350, 1 250, 1 210, 1 180, 1 070 cm⁻¹, $\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) (MeOH) 266 (4 32), 350 (4 23), *m/z* 448 (*M*⁺), 287 (*M*⁺-glucose), ¹H nmr δ (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 8.05 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 6.9 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 6.42 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz), 6.21 (H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz), 5.45 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz), 3.8–3.0 (6H) The chemical shifts of compound **1** are in good agreement with that of kaempferol-3-*O*- β -D-glucoside² Acid hydrolysis of **1** (40 mg) with 5% HCl (7 ml) gave an aglycone (12 mg), m p 280^o, which was crystallised from methanol as yellow needles and identified as kaempferol by uv, ir, ¹H and ¹³C nmr The filtrate from the reaction mixture was evaporated under reduced pressure and chromatographed on silica gel using CHCl₃ and MeOH as eluents to yield a sugar (11 mg) which was identified as D-glucose on comparison with authentic sample (pc and glc), [α]_D + 52^o (c 1.1 MeOH) Its trimethylsilyl ether was identical with an authentic sample on glc, *t*_R 8.8 and 13.4 min (column temperature 170^o)

Compound **2** was obtained as yellow needles, m p 195–200^o (MeOH), [α]_D-20^o (c=1.0 MeOH), $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 370, 1 654, 1 600, 1 500, 1 450, 1 360, 1 210, 1 170, 840, 800 cm⁻¹, $\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) (MeOH) 266 (4 31), 350 (4 21), *m/z* 448 (*M*⁺-rhamnose), 287 (448-glucose), ¹H nmr δ (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 7.99 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 6.89 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 6.42 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz), 6.22 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz) 5.32 (1H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz, anomeric proton of glucose), 4.41 (1H, s, methyl of rhamnose) The ¹³C nmr spectrum showed similar signals to those

of compound **1** together with additional rhamnosyl signals. The differences of the chemical shifts around C-6 of glucosyl moiety were considered to be caused by glycosidation. The structure of compound **2** was confirmed as kaempferol-3-*O*- α -L-rhamnosyl-(1 $\rightarrow$ 6)- β -D-glucoside (kaempferol-3-*O*-rutinoside) by comparison of ^{13}C nmr data with those of the authentic specimen². Acid hydrolysis of compound **2** (40 mg) with 5% ethanolic HCl (10 ml) gave an aglycone (12 mg), m.p. 280° which was also identified as kaempferol by uv, ir, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr and by comparison with authentic samples. The filtrate from the reaction mixture was evaporated under reduced pressure and chromatographed on silica gel using CHCl_3 and MeOH to yield two sugars which were identified as D-glucose (13 mg) and L-rhamnose (8

mg) by pc, glc and specific rotation. One sugar, D-glucose had $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 52^\circ$ (c 1.1 MeOH). Its trimethylsilyl ether was identical with an authentic sample on glc, t_{R} 8.8 and 13.4 min (column temperature 170°). The other sugar, L-rhamnose had $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 14^\circ$ (c 0.6, H₂O). Its trimethyl silyl ether was identified with an authentic sample on glc, t_{R} 4.0 and 4.5 min (column temperature 170°)

References

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